

Phloroglucinol based azo dyes for colouration of jute fabric

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Abstract : Two phloroglucinol based azo dyes namely, 2-nitro-2',4',6'-trihydroxyazobenzene (1) and 4-nitro-2',4',6'-trihydroxyazobenzene (2) have been synthesized and characterized. The two azo dyes containing azo group chromophore and nitro and hydroxyl groups as auxochrome have been applied for dyeing of bleached jute fabric in alkaline medium following the conventional exhaust method. The performance of the dyes is evaluated by evaluating the dyeing characteristics viz. colour yield and wash fastness of the dyed fabric samples. Dye II gives high dye exhaustion and colour yield with good wash fastness indicating its potential for application in dyeing jute.

Keywords : Jute fabric, bleaching, dyeing, azo dye, dye exhaustion.

Introduction

Value addition to jute has been an important activity for the jute industry to find its alternate uses through diversification as its traditional packaging sector is gradually shrinking due to challenges from cheap synthetic products. Jute is now used in various diversified products like upholstery, soft luggage, design hand bags and even in apparel sectors. Production of colourful, decorative value-added items from jute requires bleaching, dyeing and finishing of the fabric for bright shades of attractive look and better feel. Azo dyes have emerged as an important class of synthetic dyes having fastness and brilliant shades of colour for dyeing of diverse materials like textiles, leather, metal, etc. They are relatively cheap, easy to use and provide bright colour shades and fastness to textiles. Considering these attributes, azo dyes are used extensively in jute industry for dyeing jute fabric for manufacture of diversified products. Dyeing of jute fabric with several classes of dyes viz. acid, basic, direct and azo dyes has been reported earlier by several workers¹. In the present work, the synthesis and characterization of two phloroglucinol based azo dyes, viz. 2-nitro-2',4',6'-trihydroxyazobenzene and 4-nitro-2',4',6'-trihydroxyazobenzene and their performance in dyeing jute fabric

by conventional hot dyeing process in alkaline medium have been reported.

Materials and methods :

Fabric : A plain weave gray jute fabric having following specification was used; Warp : 65 ends/dm (count, 152 tex); Weft : 71 ends/dm (count, 160 tex); Fabric mass : 220 g/sq.m (at 65% RH and 30 °C).

Chemicals : The following analytical grade chemicals (~99% purity) from S.D. Fine-chem Ltd. were used for the preparation of dyes : *o*-nitroaniline, *p*-nitroaniline, phloroglucinol, conc. HCl (12 N), sodium nitrite and sodium hydroxide. For bleaching and dyeing of jute fabric following analytical grade reagents of about 99% purity from S.D. Fine-chem Ltd. viz. hydrogen peroxide, tri-sodium phosphate, sodium hydroxide, sodium carbonate, sodium silicate, sodium sulphate and acetic acid were used. Non-ionic detergent Ultravon JU (a commercial ethylene oxide condensation product of Hindustan Ciba-Giegy Ltd.) was used for soaping of dyed fabric.

Preparation of 2-nitro-2',4',6'-trihydroxyazobenzene (1) :

2-Nitroaniline (3.5 g) was dissolved in 100 ml of (0.5 N) HCl. The solution (pH 1–2) was cooled in a freezing

mixture and diazotized by dropwise addition of cooled (0 °C) saturated solution of sodium nitrite (3 g) (pH 4–5). The diazotized product thus formed was added slowly to cooled (0–5 °C) alkaline solution of phloroglucinol (3.17 g). The resultant mixture was acidified with (2 N) HCl when a brilliant reddish brown dye was obtained. It was filtered through suction, washed thoroughly with double distilled water till free from acid. The yield of the dye was 3.45 g showing 50% conversion.

Preparation of 4-nitro-2',4',6'-trihydroxyazobenzene (2) :

The method for the preparation of dye I was repeated for preparation of dye II using 4-nitroaniline (4 g) in (0.5 N) HCl solution (pH 1–2), which was diazotized by dropwise addition of cooled (0 °C) saturated solution of sodium nitrite (3 g) followed by reaction with alkaline solution of phloroglucinol (3.6 g) at low temperature (0–5 °C). The yield of the dye was 4.11 g showing 52% conversion.

Structural elucidation of dyes :

Dye I (2-Nitro-2',4',6'-trihydroxyazobenzene) : The azo dye was synthesized by diazotization of *o*-nitroaniline followed by coupling with alkaline solution of phloroglucinol. The elemental analysis data found (calcd.) : C, 52.31 (52.36); H, 3.24 (3.27); N, 15.23 (15.27).

Dye II (4-Nitro-2',4',6'-trihydroxyazobenzene) : The azo dye was synthesized by diazotization of *p*-nitroaniline followed by coupling with alkaline solution of phloroglucinol. The elemental analysis data found (calcd.) : C, 52.31 (52.36); H, 3.24 (3.27); N, 15.23 (15.28).

Infra-red spectra : The infra-red spectra of the dyes I and II were recorded over a range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ on a Jasco-4200 FTIR spectrometer making KBr pellets of the two dyes. Dye I showed peaks at 3657.3 cm⁻¹ and 1595.0 cm⁻¹ characteristic of aromatic -O-H and -N=N- groups respectively. The absorption at 1336.9 cm⁻¹ and 1523.7 cm⁻¹ indicate presence of C-NO₂ group. The absorption peaks at 1220.9 cm⁻¹ and 1305.7 cm⁻¹ are characteristic of aromatic O-H bending and C-O stretching respectively. In dye II, the characteristic peaks of aromatic -O-H and -N=N- groups appear at 3666.9 cm⁻¹ and 1614.3 cm⁻¹ respectively while the absorption at 1344.3 cm⁻¹ and 1525.6 cm⁻¹ indicate presence of C-NO₂ group.

Bleaching of jute fabric :

Conventional bleaching of grey jute fabric was performed in a closed vessel containing hydrogen peroxide (2 vol), trisodium phosphate (5 g/L), sodium hydroxide (1 g/L), sodium silicate (10 g/L) and nonionic detergent, Ultravon JU (2 ml/L) for 2 h at 90 °C with a material to liquor ratio 1 : 20. The pH of the bath was maintained at 10. After bleaching, the fibre samples were washed thoroughly in cold water, neutralized with acetic acid (2 ml/L), washed again and finally dried.

Dyeing of bleached jute fabric :

Bleached jute fabric samples were dyed with the two azo dyes by direct dyeing process. The dye was first converted to sodium salt for solubilization and the solubilized dye was then applied to fabric by direct dyeing process.

Pasting and solubilisation : Dye (4% , owf) was pasted with a little Ultravon JU and warm water. Sodium carbonate (half the weight of the dye) was added to the paste, then added hot water to make the volume 100 ml. The dye solution (pH 9–10) was heated for 10 min at 80 °C.

Dyeing : Dye bath was made with the dissolved dye (4% owf), sodium hydroxide (1 gpl) and sodium sulphate (5 gpl) and the material to liquor ratio was kept at 1 : 20. The bleached jute fabric sample was treated in the dye bath at 80 °C for one hour for dyeing. The sample was then washed thoroughly with cold water, soaped with Ultravon JU (2 gpl) in a water bath (M/L ratio, 1 : 20) at 50 °C for 15 min followed by washing thoroughly with cold water and drying in air.

Determination of physico-chemical properties :

The whiteness index on the Hunter scale, yellowness index on the ASTM D1925 scale and brightness index on the TAPPI 452 scale of grey and bleached jute fabric samples were evaluated by the Spectrascan-5100® computerized colour matching system with relevant software. Absorbency of grey and bleached jute fabric samples was determined as specified in IS : 2369–1967^{2a}. The dyed jute fabric samples were subjected to wash fastness test in a Launder-o-Meter as specified in IS : 3361–1979^{2b}. The wash fastness rating of all dyed jute fabric samples were evaluated with a computerized colour matching system.

Table 1. Optical and absorbance properties of grey and bleached jute fabric

Jute sample	Whiteness index (Hunter)	Yellowness index (ASTMD 1925)	Brightness index (TAPPI 452)	Absorbency (s)
Grey	51.73	48.15	21.15	90
Bleached	79.50	24.94	57.08	4

Table 2. Performance of synthesized dyes on bleached jute fabrics

Dye sample	λ_{\max} (nm) of dye solution	λ_{\max} (nm) of dye solution after dyeing	Dye exhaustion (%)	λ_{\max} (nm) of dyed fabric	K/S value	Reflectance (%)	Wash fastness
2-Nitro-2',4',6'-trihydroxy-azobenzene (Dye I)	406.4	400.8	5.04	470	3.9	10.30	3-4
4-Nitro-2',4',6'-trihydroxy-azobenzene (Dye II)	451.0	445.0	53.51	490	13.5	3.44	4

Dye exhaustion (%) was determined from the expression $[(x - y)/x] \times 100$, where x and y are concentrations of dye solution before and after dyeing of fabric respectively. The concentration of dye solution was determined by measuring the absorbance of a standard and experimental dye solutions at λ_{\max} , with UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Hitachi, Model 3410). The Spectrascan-5100[®] computerized colour matching system was used to measure the λ_{\max} , reflectance and K/S values of dyed jute fabric samples using the following formula : $K/S = [(1 - R)/2R] \propto C$, where K , the coefficient of absorption, S , the coefficient of scattering, R , the reflectance of substrate at λ_{\max} and C , the concentration of dye. The K/S value is an index of the dye uptake or colour yield.

Results and discussion

Jute is a natural lignocellulosic fibre containing α -cellulose (~60%), hemicelluloses (~23%), and lignin (~14%) besides some minor constituents like lipids, ash, pectin, etc. Pretreatment of fabric with alkaline hydrogen peroxide bleaching produces clean fabric with improved optical and absorbance properties shown in Table 1.

Band characterization³ of FTIR spectra of the two dyes showed the presence of azo group and characteristic aromatic hydroxyl and nitro groups in both the dyes. The dyes I and II are partially soluble in water but completely soluble in alkaline medium (pH 9–10). Due to presence of azo chromophore and auxochrome groups the compounds have affinity towards jute and can be treated as

dyes for jute textile. The performance of the two dyes applied to jute fabric is reported in Table 2. The significant difference in λ_{\max} values and dye exhaustion (%) is attributed to the difference in chemical structure of the two dyes. Colour yield of dyed fabric is measured by K/S value and shows direct relationship with dye exhaustion (%). As the dye exhaustion (%) is low in dye I, colour yield measured by K/S value is also found low with high reflectance (%). Wash fastness is good for both the dyes I and II which might be due to the presence of three hydroxyl groups in both dyes. The investigation shows satisfactory performance of dye II with high dye exhaustion, colour yield and good wash fastness that may find application in jute dyeing.

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References

- (a) S. N. Pandey, S. N. Chattopadhyay, N. C. Pan and A. Day, *Textile Dyer & Printer*, 1993, **26**, 23; (b) S. N. Chattopadhyay, N. C. Pan and A. Day, *J. Textile Institute*, 2002, **93**, 306; (c) S. N. Pandey, S. N. Chattopadhyay, N. C. Pan and A. Day, *Indian J. Fibre Text Res.*, 1994, **19**, 34; (d) M. B. Saha, R. N. Patra, S. K. Chakraborty and Pankaj Giri, *Colourage*, 2004, **52**, 10; (e) Prasanti K. Saha and M.

- B. Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1995, **72**, 755; (f) A. Day, S. N. Chattopadhyay, Kalyan Pandey, Pankaj Giri, Swapan Bhattacharya and M. B. Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **83**, 311; (g) Jayanta Sarkhel, S. K Bhaduri, S. N. Chattopadhyay, T. Deb and M. B. Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 1020.
2. (a) IS : 2369-1967; (b) IS : 3361-1979, ISI Handbook of Textile Testing, BIS, New Delhi, 1982.
 3. John R. Dyer, "Applications of Absorption Spectroscopy of Organic Molecules", 6th ed., Prentice-Hall, Inc, New York, 1987.